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TITLE

AUTHOR(S) & AFFILIATION(S)

ABSTRACT

Please use Normal style, **the abstract should be longer from 400 and 600 words** and present: a) Aims of the initiative presented; b) Main results achieved; c) Impacts expected.

Please specify if the abstract is for a:

Onsite oral presentation

Digital poster

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